

and 70 days after germination.

Sowing upland rice in savanna soils is not recommended because the varieties lack tolerance for excessive exchangeable aluminum, the most limiting factor in those soils. □

Effect of time of burying of Dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata* on nitrogen economy in paddy

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The crop recovers only about 15 to 40% of applied nitrogen in submerged paddy soils. The recent increase in paddy cultivation in nontraditional, light-textured soils in northeastern India has further aggravated the problem. It is important to develop a technology to increase the efficiency of nitrogen utilization and to conserve the nitrogen harnessed through green manure.

An experiment to test the relationship of Dhaincha (*Sesbania*) green manure to nitrogen economy was initiated at the PAU farm, Ludhiana, in 1977 kharif.

Effect on paddy yield of different times of burying Dhaincha.^a Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India.

Days buried before puddling	Grain yield (t/ha)				Av.
	No N	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	
Fallow	2.4	4.7	5.2	5.5	4.5
20	4.2	5.8	5.7	5.5	5.3
10	5.0	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.4
0	5.7	5.6	5.6	6.2	5.1
Av.	4.1	5.4	5.5	5.7	

^aC.D. at 5% for N level: 5.7; C.D. for dates: 5.7; C.D. for dates × N level: 6.1

PAU presently recommends the burying of green manure about 2 weeks before transplanting paddy — which means that Dhaincha should be sown by the second or third week of April, when farmers are busy with the rabi harvest and postharvest operations. Because farmers are reluctant to include green manure in their cropping pattern, an experiment to determine the optimum time to bury Dhaincha without adversely affecting paddy yield was designed. (Dhaincha buried immediately before transplanting was thought to adversely affect crop growth because of nitrogen immobilization, low Eh value, and

formation of organic acid on higher partial CO₂ pressure.) But it was more beneficial to bury Dhaincha at puddling than at 20 or 10 days before puddling (see table). Interestingly, it saved 120 kg N/ha. The recommended method saved only 60 kg N/ha. The new technique makes conservation of 100% more nitrogen possible, and gives farmers 15 more days to plan their Dhaincha sowing during the busy season.

The experiment was repeated in 1978 at the PAU farm and in farmers' fields in Ludhiana district. Effects on crop growth seem similar. Investigations will be reported. □

Effects of leaf area index and spacing on the productivity of Pankaj

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The longduration variety Pankaj (a selection of IR5) was transplanted at the Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, in the 1977 kharif using a strip-plot design with three replications. Two rates of nitrogen — N₁ (50 kg N/ha) and N₂, (100 kg N/ha) — and five spacings — S₁ (10 × 10 cm), S₂ (15 × 15 cm), S₃ (20 × 20 cm), S₄ (25 × 25 cm), and S₅ (30 × 30 cm) — were used. Basal treatments of superphosphate and muriate were used for all plots at 60 kg P₂O₅/ha and 40 kg K₂O/ha. The leaf area index (LAI) was recorded at five stages: maximum tillering, panicle initiation, ear emergence, dough, and ripening. The final yield was recorded.

Grain yield in relation to leaf area index and plant spacing at the Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, India.

Treatment ^a	Leaf area index					Yield (t/ha)
	Maximum tillering	Panicle initiation	Ear emergence	Dough	Ripening	
N ₁ S ₁	3.0	4.2	9.4	9.2	7.8	5.9
N ₂ S ₁	3.5	1.3	9.7	8.9	8.2	5.6
N ₁ S ₂	3.9	3.7	11.1	6.0	7.1	6.3
N ₂ S ₂	4.3	3.4	7.4	9.0	5.2	6.3
N ₁ S ₃	1.4	2.4	5.7	6.7	4.1	5.8
N ₂ S ₃	1.0	3.3	5.6	5.5	3.4	6.6
N ₁ S ₄	1.8	3.7	4.7	5.3	3.9	5.8
N ₂ S ₄	1.8	3.2	4.9	5.2	3.9	6.1
N ₁ S ₅	0.7	2.1	3.5	4.9	2.6	4.1
N ₂ S ₅	1.0	2.2	3.2	4.9	2.5	4.9

^aN₁ = 50 kg N/ha, N₂ = 100 kg N/ha, S₁ = 10 × 10 cm, S₂, = 15 × 15 cm, S₃, = 20 × 20 cm, S₄, = 25 × 25 cm, S₅, = 30 × 30 cm.

The results show that the LAI at ear emergence and at the dough stage was related to yield. The LAI was visibly higher in the close spacing than in the wide spacing.

Pankaj yielded higher at 15- × 15-cm

spacing with 50 kg N/ha and at 20 × 20 cm with 100 kg N/ha. Spacings greater than 25 cm between plants adversely affected yields. There was no yield response to the second 50 kg N/ha. □